

1 **Homeobox activation in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.**

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7 We recently identified homeobox factors as essential for transformation, suggesting that their inhibition in
8 the clinic, like in patients with difficult to treat metastatic cancer, will be unavoidably favorable. We
9 measured total transcription in lung metastasis and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer
10 using whole transcriptome technologies to identify a homeobox signature in the lung metastasis. Most
11 prominent in activation was Tbx3 and Tbx4. Sox5, Sox10, Sox15 and Sox17 were silenced while Sox13
12 was moderately activated. Activation of Foxd4, Foxj1, Foxo6 and Foxh1 indicated a special function for
13 specific Fox family homeoboxes in lung metastasis. Master homeobox factors Pax1 and Tgif2 were also
14 activated and expressed at very high levels. A wide variety of developmentally-potent or oncogenic
15 homeobox transcription factors are active in lung metastasis in breast cancer.

16 Citations

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